

ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPACTS OF DIVESTMENT ON PROJECT MATURATION IN THE NIGERIAN OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY

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Abstract: *This study examined the impact of divestment on project maturation in the Nigerian oil and gas industry. The increasing divestment by multinational companies and demand for local participation in the Nigerian oil and gas industry have necessitated the need to investigate how divestment impacts project maturation in the sector. Given this, the objectives of the study were to determine how divestment affects project timelines and budgeting. A quantitative research design was adopted. The study examined twenty-six (26) oil and gas projects in Nigeria using data obtained from the Nigerian Upstream Petroleum Regulatory Commission (NUPRC). Empirical results showed that post-divestment projects had a higher average timeline efficiency score of 2.69 compared to 0.86 for pre-divestment projects, indicating enhanced delivery speed. In terms of budgeting, cost variance ratio for post-divestment projects was 0.65 versus 0.53 for pre-divestment projects, reflecting leaner operations but more variability in cost control. These findings underscore the dual potential of divestment to enhance project agility and local participation, while also revealing capacity gaps requiring institutional support. The study concluded that divestment, if properly managed, can catalyze project efficiency, industry indigenization, and long-term sustainability in Nigeria's energy sector.*

Keywords: *Asset Divestment, Project Maturation, Nigerian Oil and Gas Industry, International Oil Companies (IOCs), Energy Transition*

I. INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

There is a significant transformation in the Nigerian oil and gas industry in recent years. One of the major issues in the industry is the divestment of assets by International Oil Companies (IOCs). Divestment has significant impact on project maturation processes in the Nigerian oil and gas industry. As noted by Imoisi (2024), divestment is a strategic decision involving the sale or disposal of business

units, assets, or operations. In context of this study, divestment refers to the act of selling, transferring, or disposing of assets, investments, or business interests. According to Asikhia (2022), divestment is commonly undertaken by individuals, companies, or organizations to reduce or eliminate their involvement in certain investments. The decision to divest is often driven by portfolio rebalancing, ethical, financial, or strategic considerations. This process may include selling stocks, bonds, or other assets, as well as exiting partnerships or business ventures (Imoisi, 2024). Divestment is frequently associated with efforts to withdraw support from industries or companies perceived to be socially or environmentally harmful (Imoisi, 2024). This trend has been partly influenced by the global energy transition, as companies pivot towards cleaner energy sources to mitigate climate change impacts (Oruwari *et al.*, 2024).

The operational settings of projects have been fundamentally altered by this shift. According to Imoisi (2024), Nigeria has already witnessed assets worth \$21 billion being divested. This trend presents both opportunities and challenges to the Nigerian oil and gas industry. Asikhia (2022) asserted that the divestment trend has become a critical factor that influences project maturation processes across oil and gas value chain in Nigeria. The author noted that this transition period has introduced unprecedented challenges in project execution. This is particularly pronounced in maintaining operational continuity and technical expertise. As observed by Olakada *et al.* (2024), the complexity of these challenges is amplified in off-shore operations. This is because technical requirements and capital investments in this area are substantially higher than in on-shore projects.

In view of the rich hydrocarbon reserve and complex-economic dynamics of Nigeria, it is no doubt a good case study to understand the impact of divestment on project maturation in shallow and deep-water fields. The oil and gas industry in Nigeria has long been reckoned as the corner stone of the Nigeria's economy. However, Olakada *et al.* (2024) claimed that the industry still faces challenges such as aging infrastructure, regulatory inefficiencies, and environmental concerns. Omotuyi (2023) lamented that these problems were exacerbated by continued divestment of international oil companies (IOCs) from Nigerian assets. The author attributed this problem to declining profitability, stringent environmental regulations, and security risks in operating environments. However, Imoisi (2024) asserted that the main drivers behind the divestments in Nigeria's oil and gas sector are the regulatory uncertainties that persisted until the enactment of the Petroleum Industry Act in 2021.

There is no gainsaying that these divestments have opened opportunities for indigenous companies to increase their participation in the Nigerian oil and gas industry. The only concern here is that it also has the potential to complicate project maturation timelines, cost management, and technical operations. To buttress this claim, a historical analysis of oil and gas industry in Nigeria revealed that project maturation in the industry relied heavily on the expertise and financial capacity of the IOCs (Okoro *et al.*, 2021; Bakare *et al.*, 2024). With divestment, there is a paradigm shift where indigenous companies are increasingly taking leadership roles in project execution. According to Olakada *et al.*

(2024), this transition has implications for project timelines, cost management, and technical execution capabilities, particularly in complex offshore environments.

The relationship between divestment and project timelines is quite complex. According to Yawale *et al* (2023), divestment often leads to disruptions in project schedules due to changes in ownership, operational strategies, and funding structures. These challenges are even worsened by the Nigerian context characterised regulatory hurdles and bureaucratic delays. In addition, divestments have also influenced project costs, particularly in managing the capital (CAPEX) and operational expenditure (OPEX). Asikhia (2022) highlighted that divestiture impacts financial planning accuracy, often requiring significant adjustments in budgets to align with new ownership goals. These adjustments often necessitate new financial planning frameworks and risk management strategies, particularly for indigenous companies assuming control of divested assets.

Against this backdrop, this study therefore seeks to bridge these investigative areas by exploring the impacts of divestment on project maturation in Nigeria's oil and gas industry. The focus of the study on variables such as timeline compliance and cost adjustments shows that the study is poised to offer actionable recommendations for stakeholders navigating divestment in the industry.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aims to assess the impact of divestment on project maturation in the Nigerian oil and gas industry. The specific objective of the study are;

- i. To determine the impact of divestment on project timelines in the Nigerian oil and gas industry.
- ii. To analyze the effects of divestment on project costs and budgeting in the Nigerian oil and gas industry.

The Research Questions

This study poses the following research question to guide its investigation.

- i. How does divestment impact project timelines in the Nigerian oil and gas industry?
- ii. What are the effects of divestment on project costs and budgeting in the Nigerian oil and gas industry?

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Theoretical Framework

Resource-Based Theory

Resource-Based Theory (RBT) was initially conceptualized by Wernerfelt in 1984 and further developed by Barney in 1991. As observed by Bertram and Bertram (2016), the theory has become a cornerstone of strategic management literature. The theory posits that the competitive advantage of a firm arises primarily from its internal resources, which must be valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable (VRIN). This theoretical foundation is situated to the context of this study to understand how divestment in the oil and gas industry impacts resource allocation, project maturation, and overall organizational performance.

The oil and gas industry is characterized by its dependence on both tangible and intangible resources. Tangible resources include capital-intensive physical assets such as rigs, refineries, and pipelines. Intangible resources on the other hand encompass knowledge, expertise, patents, and stakeholder relationships. RBT provides a structured framework for assessing the strategic value of these resources during divestment. For example, Mas'oud Al-Hanshi, Ojiako, and Williams (2020) demonstrated that organizational resources in petroleum projects significantly impact performance when aligned with VRIN principles. The findings of the authors emphasized the importance of “valuable” and “organizationally supported” resources in addressing operational complexities during strategic transitions such as divestment. This highlights the necessity of prioritizing resource alignment to mitigate disruptions during project maturation.

One critical aspect of RBT is its emphasis on resource immobility, which assumes that certain strategic resources cannot be easily transferred or replicated across firms. In divestment scenarios, this concept is particularly relevant. This is because the reallocation of resources whether through asset sales or organizational restructuring can lead to a loss of competitive advantage. Osobajo and Bjeirmi (2021) examined the role of tacit knowledge in creating competitive advantage within the oil and gas sector. The study found that tacit knowledge, as a resource, plays a mediating role in enhancing organizational performance. However, its transferability during divestment processes is limited. This shows the importance of retaining such critical knowledge assets to ensure continuity and project success. This finding underscores the necessity of adopting strategic measures to manage and preserve intangible resources during divestment.

Furthermore, RBT underscores the importance of deploying resources in a manner that creates value. Elbanna and Abdel-Maksoud (2020) highlighted the role of financial and human resources in influencing the performance of public organizations in an oil-rich country. The authors observed that resource slack, particularly in financial resources, significantly impacted organizational performance. Applying this insight to divestment in the oil and gas sector suggests that firms must carefully evaluate which resources to retain and which to divest to optimize project outcomes and maintain financial flexibility. This perspective is particularly pertinent in the Nigerian oil and gas industry, where divestment decisions often intersect with regulatory pressures and market volatility.

Research Gap

A critical review of empirical works reveals several notable gaps in the existing literature on the impacts of divestment on project maturation in the oil and gas industry, particularly in the Nigerian context. While numerous studies have addressed related themes, key areas remain underexplored or inadequately addressed, which this study aims to address. First, the impact of divestment on project timelines in the Nigerian oil and gas industry remains insufficiently examined. Although studies like those of Asikhia (2022) and Lawal, Nwoye, and Ibrahim (2023) have discussed broader factors influencing project performance, they do not specifically focus on how divestment activities influence

project delays or acceleration in different operational environments. This leaves a contextual void in understanding regional and sectorial differences. Second, the effect of divestment on project costs and budgeting, particularly in high-capital, long-term investments such as deep-water oil fields, has not been rigorously analyzed. While Atolagbe and Mohammed (2022) examined cost control measures in the sector, their focus was on technological and operational innovations. Thus, the studies did not address how divestment shapes budgetary outcomes and resource allocation decisions in complex projects. This study fills these gaps by providing an integrated analysis of the impacts of divestment.

III. THE RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study adopts quantitative research design. As noted by Fischer, Boone and Neumann (2023), this method is characterized by its focus on numerical data, statistical analysis, and objective measurements. Thus, it allows for a systematic evaluation of relationships between variables. In view of this, this method is therefore deemed a good fit to analyze the impacts of divestments on project maturation in the Nigerian oil and gas industry. The use of quantitative approach in this study facilitated the exploration of how divestment influences project timelines and project costs. This design is appropriate for this study because it enables a detailed examination of the relationships between divestment and project maturation indicators through statistical techniques.

Area of the Study

The study area is the Niger Delta region of Nigeria, located between latitudes 4°00'N and 6°30'N and longitudes 3°00'E and 9°00'E (Uwadiae Oyegun, Lawal & Ogoro, 2023). The region lies along the Atlantic coastline in southern Nigeria and comprises nine oil-producing states, including Rivers, Bayelsa, Delta, and Akwa Ibom. It features extensive river networks, mangrove swamps, wetlands, and both urban and rural settlements. The Niger Delta hosts the highest concentration of oil and gas infrastructure in the country, including onshore, swamp, and shallow-water assets. This region provides a suitable context for the study due to its dominance in Nigeria's oil and gas production and its long history of asset ownership transitions. Divestment activities by multinational companies occur predominantly within this area. The operational density and regulatory complexity of the Niger Delta also support a rigorous examination of project timelines within a realistic industry setting.

Source of Data

The data employed in this study was obtained from Nigerian Upstream Petroleum Regulatory Commission (NUPRC). Furthermore, academic journals, books, and prior research studies provided theoretical and empirical context to support the analysis.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Evaluation of the First Objective

This subsection presents the analysis corresponding to Research Question One, which seeks to determine “How does divestment impact project timelines in the Nigerian oil and gas industry?” This

section interprets the statistical relationships and patterns observed between divestment activities and project delivery schedules. The analyzed project timelines with efficiency scores for pre-divestment projects are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Analyzed project timelines with efficiency scores for pre-divestment projects

S/N	Project Title	Company Name	Licence/Lease	Start Date	Estimated Completion Date	Duration (Months)	Percentage Completion (%)	Current Project Phase	Timeline Efficiency Score
1	Kolo Creek F-Sand Compression Project	Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC)	OML 28	2019-04-30	2028-12-31	116.0	0	CDA/FEED	0.00
2	Soku Nodal Compression	SPDC	OML 23	2018-10-15	2023-02-16	52.0	N/A	Suspended	N/A
3	Escravos Community Electrification Interdependency Power Project	SPDC	SPDC Escravos Flowstation Communities	2024-09-14	2025-09-14	12.0	0	DED	0.00

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S/N	Project Title	Company Name	Licence /Lease	Start Date	Estimated Completion	Duration	Percent Completion	Current Project Phase	Timeline
4	JV Product ion Facilities Metering Upgrade Project	Chevron Nigeria Limited	Western Zone Fields	2022-11-01	2025-12-31	37.9	40	Procurement/Construction/Fabrication/Installation	1.06
5	NLNG to BOGT Condensate Divert Project	SPDC	OML 29	2022-12-31	2025-09-14	32.5	40	Commissioning	1.23
6	North Offshore Area Produced Water Disposal Project	Chevron Nigeria Limited	OML 95	2022-03-01	2025-12-31	45.9	N/A	DED	N/A
7	EPU Phase 3	SPDC	OML 28	2019-06-10	2027-06-30	96.7	5	CDA/FEE D	0.05
8	Gbaran Single Wells	SPDC	OML 28	2022-03-09	2024-12-31	33.7	52.99	Pre-Commissioning	1.57
9	OML 100	TotalEnergies	OML 100	2021-03-31	2024-10-31	43.0	91.81	Procurement/Construction	2.14

S/N	Project Title	Company Name	Licence/Lease	Start Date	Estimated Completion Date	Percent Completion	Duration (Months)	Current Project Phase	Timeline Efficiency
10	Gbaran Nodal Compression Project	SPDC	OML 28	2018-06-30	2024-12-31	78.1	97	Procurement/Construction/Fabrication/Installation	1.24
11	CNL JV Vent Gas Management Project	Chevron Nigeria Limited	Multiple PMLs	2021-02-08	2025-12-31	58.6	40	DED	0.68

Table 1 presents a detailed breakdown of project timelines for 11 pre-divestment projects in the Nigerian oil and gas industry, managed by international oil companies (IOCs) such as Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC) and Chevron Nigeria Limited. It provides a comprehensive view of pre-divestment project attributes including start and estimated completion dates, duration in months, percent completion, current project phase, and timeline efficiency scores. The data, spanning from 2018 to 2024, reveals an average duration of 55.6 months and an average timeline efficiency score of 0.86 which indicate a typically longer and less efficient timelines associated with IOC-led initiatives. To provide a more robust understanding of these dynamics, the analysis is taken further with the analysis of project timelines with efficiency scores for post-divestment projects as summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Analyzed project timelines with efficiency scores for post-divestment projects

S/N	Project Title	Company Name	Licence/Lease	Start Date	Estimated Completion Date	Percent Completion	Duration (Months)	Current Project Phase	Timeline Efficiency
1	20KBPD Otakikpo Flowstation Facility Project	Green Energy International Limited	OML 11	2023-05-18	2024-10-31	99.5	17.45	Procurement/Construction/Fabrication/Installation	5.72

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2	Provision of FEED and DED of Aroh 1 & 2 Well Jacket and Aroh Field Manifold	NNPC Limited	E&P	OML 49	2022-12-07	2024-12-31	24.8	50	DED	2.02
3	Seplat Flare Gas Meter Changeout	Seplat		OML 40	2023-09-27	2024-12-31	15.1	10	CDA/FEED	0.66
4	Produced Water Re-injection Surface Facility	Platform Petroleum Limited		OML 38	2023-02-16	2024-12-31	22.5	25	CDA/FEED	1.11
5	Assa Field Re-development Project	Waltersmith Petroman Oil Limited		OML 21	2022-09-01	2024-12-31	27.9	15	Suspended	0.54
6	Installation of Temporary 5,000BOP D EPF at Oki-Oziengbe Flowstation	Enageed Resources Limited		OML 148	2023-06-15	2024-08-31	14.5	100	Commissioning	6.90

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7	Egbaoma Platform Flowstation Debottlenecking and Upgrade 2.0	Petroleum Limited & Newcross Petroleum Limited	OML 38	2023-06-14	2024-12-31	18.6	87	Pre-Commissioning	4.68
8	Design and Construction of 2 x 100,000 BBLs Storage Tanks	Midwestern Oil & Gas Company Limited	OML 56	2023-07-15	2025-06-30	23.5	3	CDA/FEED	0.13
9	EPCIC for 2 x 40,000 bbls. Crude Oil Storage Tanks	NNPC Limited/FHN JV	E&P OML 26	2022-10-28	2023-12-31	14.1	23	Procurement/Construction/Fabrication/Installation	1.63

S/N	Project Title	Company Name	Licence/Lease	Start Date	Estimated Completion	Duration (Months)	Percent Completed	Current Project Phase	Timeline Efficiency
10	10KBO PD Engineering Procurement, Construction,	Kalm Marine Petroleum Services Limited	PPL 212	2023-07-16	2024-12-31	17.5	69.7	Procurement/Construction/Fabrication/Installation	3.98

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	Installation and Commissioning								
11	Ogbelle Flowstation Modification	Aradel Energy	OML 54	2023-12-02	2024-12-31	12.9	60	Procurement/Construction/Fabrication/Installation	4.65
12	SGEPL Oquali-Ukpichi Facility Project	Sterling Global Exploration and Production Limited	OML 157	2023-09-24	2024-10-31	13.2	10	DED	0.76
13	Okwok Field Development Project	Oriental Energy Resources Limited	OML 67	2021-12-01	2025-02-28	38.9	83	Procurement/Construction/Fabrication/Installation	2.13
14	750,000 Capacity Otakikpo Onshore Terminal	Green Energy International Limited	OML 11	2023-09-01	2025-02-28	17.9	76.39	Procurement/Construction/Fabrication/Installation	4.27

al Project									
15	Anyala/Madu Integrated Project	First Exploration and Petroleum Development Ltd.	OML 83 & 85	2018-08-26	2026-09-30	97.2	N/A	Commissioning	N/A

Table 2 provides a detailed overview of project timelines for 15 post-divestment projects in the Nigerian oil and gas industry, managed by local oil companies (LOCs) such as Green Energy International Limited and Seplat. The table (4.10) focuses on projects following divestment, presenting key metrics including start and estimated completion dates, duration in months, percent completion, current project phase, and timeline efficiency scores. Covering the period from 2018 to 2025, the data indicates an average duration of 25.9 months and an average timeline efficiency score of 2.69, highlighting a shift toward shorter and more efficient project cycles under LOC management.

Table 4.9 analyzed project duration and progress for pre-divestment project while Table 4.10 analyzed the same parameters for post-divestment projects. In both cases, project duration was calculated as the difference between start and estimated completion dates. Timeline efficiency score ((Percentage completion/Duration (months)) × 100) was derived to assess progress efficiency. The analysis revealed significant differences in project timelines. Pre-divestment projects presented in Table 1, have an average duration of 55.6 months (median: 45.9 months, range: 12.0–116.0 months). Post-divestment projects shown in Table 2, average 25.9 months (median: 18.6 months, range: 12.9–97.2 months). As evident in figure 1, the result suggests that local operators undertake shorter projects, possibly due to smaller scopes or operational agility.

Figure 1: Average timeline efficiency by divestment status in the Nigerian oil and gas industry
The chart of Figure 1 compares pre-divestment projects, managed primarily by international oil companies (IOCs), with post-divestment projects, overseen by indigenous local oil companies (LOCs). A striking observation from Figure 1 is the significant disparity in average timeline efficiency scores. Pre-divestment projects exhibit an average score of 0.86 which indicates slower progress relative to their duration, likely due to the complex, long-term nature of IOC-managed initiatives. In contrast, post-divestment projects achieve an average score of 2.69, which suggests a marked improvement in delivery speed. This difference underscores the potential of divestment to enhance project agility. This is possibly driven by LOCs’ focus on simpler, onshore, or shallow-water projects with shorter timelines. The bar chart in Figure 2 compares the average project durations in the Nigerian oil and gas industry, differentiated by divestment status. The chart draws data from Table 1 and 2, which lists the durations (in months) of 26 projects classified as pre-divestment and post-divestment.

Figure 2: Average project durations between pre-divestment and post-divestment projects

A key insight from Figure 2 is the notable contrast in average project durations. Pre-divestment projects average 55.6 months, reflecting the extended timelines often associated with IOC-led initiatives, which may involve complex offshore or gas-processing projects. Post-divestment projects, by contrast, average 25.9 months which is an indication of a substantial reduction in duration. This suggests that divestment enables faster project cycles, likely due to LOCs focusing on less complex, onshore, or shallow-water assets. Timeline efficiency further highlights disparities. Post-divestment projects achieve a higher average efficiency score (2.69) compared to pre-divestment projects (0.86). For instance, the post-divestment Oki-Oziengbe EPF project reached 100% completion in 14.5 months (score: 6.90), while the pre-divestment Kolo Creek project shows 0% completion after 116 months (score: 0.00). Figure 2 shows that post-divestment projects are more frequently in advanced phases compared to pre-divestment projects, which often remain in early design stages.

Evaluation of the Second Research Question

This subsection examines Research Question Two, which seeks to answer: “What are the effects of divestment on project costs and budgeting in the Nigerian oil and gas industry?” The analysis is an inquiry through comparative and inferential evaluation of pre- and post-divestment financial performance.

The section begins by analyzing the pre-divestment cost data which captured baseline expenditure levels and their corresponding cost variance ratios. These results are detailed in Table 4. This establishes a benchmark against which the financial effects of divestment can be assessed.

Table 4: Analyzed pre-divestment project costs with cost variance ratio

S/N	Project Title	Company Name	Licence/Lease	Project CAPEX (\$)	Project Cost Actual (\$)	Cost - Variance Ratio
1	Kolo Creek F-Sand Compression Project	Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC)	OML 28	216000000	0	0.0000
2	Soku Nodal Compression	SPDC	OML 23	0	0	N/A

S/N	Project Title	Company Name	Licence/Lease	Project CAPEX (\$)	Project Cost Actual (\$)	Cost - Variance Ratio
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3	Escravos Community Electrification Interdependency Power Project	SPDC	SPDC Escravos Flowstation Communities	0	0	N/A
4	JV Production Facilities Metering Upgrade Project	Chevron Nigeria Limited	Western Zone Fields	8000000	8000000	1.0000
5	NLNG to BOGT Condensate Divert Project	SPDC	OML 29	0	500000	N/A
6	North Offshore Area Produced Water Disposal Project	Chevron Nigeria Limited	OML 95	180000000	180000000	1.0000
7	EPU Phase 3	SPDC	OML 28	174000000	0	0.0000
8	Gbaran Single Wells	SPDC	OML 28	110112500	5031	0.0000
9	OML 100 Flare Reduction Project	TotalEnergies	OML 100	26800000	26800000	1.0000
10	Gbaran Nodal Compression	SPDC	OML 28	325000000	233000000	0.7169
11	CNL JV Vent Gas Management Project	Chevron Nigeria Limited	Multiple PMLs	97.55	97.55	1.0000

Table 4 details the cost profiles of 11 pre-divestment projects in the Nigerian oil and gas industry, managed by international oil companies (IOCs). It presents comprehensive data on project capital expenditure (CAPEX), actual costs, and cost variance ratios, covering projects from 2018 to 2024. The data reveals significant investments, with an average CAPEX of approximately \$98.8 million and a cost variance ratio ranging from 0.0000 to 1.0000, indicating both stalled and fully aligned cost outcomes. Subsequently, Table 5 presents the cost outcomes observed after divestment activities. The comparison between these two tables reveals shifts in budgeting efficiency, cost overruns, and expenditure control mechanisms following ownership transitions.

Table 5: Analyzed post-divestment project costs with cost variance ratio

S/N	Project Title	Company Name	Licence/Lease	Project CAPEX (\$)	Project Cost Actual (\$)	Cost - Variance Ratio
1	2 X 20KBPD Otakikpo Flowstation Facility Project	Green Energy International Limited	OML 11	30000000	29865000	0.9955
2	Provision of FEED and DED of Aroh 1 & 2 Well Jacket and Aroh Field Manifold	NNPC E&P Limited	OML 49	136971.11	136971.11	1.0000

S/N	Project Title	Company Name	Licence/Lease	Project CAPEX (\$)	Project Cost Actual (\$)	Cost - Variance Ratio
3	Seplat Flare Gas Meter Changeout	Seplat	OML 40	0	0	N/A
4	Produced Water Re-injection Surface Facility	Platform Petroleum Limited	OML 38	5184194.14	0	0.0000
5	Assa Field Re-development Project	Waltersmith Petroman Oil Limited	OML 21	1000000	1200000	1.2000
6	Installation of Temporary 5,000BOPD EPF at Oki-Oziengbe Flowstation	Enageed Resources Limited	OML 148	4602650	0	0.0000
7	Egbaoma Flowstation Debottlenecking and Upgrade 2.0	Platform Petroleum Limited & Newcross	OML 38	4700000	4700000	1.0000

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			Petroleum Limited				
8	Design and Construction of 2 x 100,000 BBLS Storage Tanks		Midwestern Oil & Gas Company Limited	OML 56	9000000	0	0.0000
9	EPCIC for 2 x 40,000 bbls. Crude Oil Storage Tanks		NNPC E&P Limited/FHN JV	OML 26	5885269.13	5885269.13	1.0000
10	10KBOPD Engineering Procurement, Construction, Installation and Commissioning	EPF	Kalm Marine Petroleum Services Limited	PPL 212	6300000	1500000	0.2381
11	Ogbelle Flowstation Modification		Aradel Energy	OML 54	508923.68	508923.68	1.0000
12	SGEPL Ukpichi Project	Oguali-Facility	Sterling Global Exploration and Production Limited	OML 157	269.12	79.8	0.2965
13	Okwok Field Development Project		Oriental Energy Resources Limited	OML 67	515000000	229617000	0.4459
14	750,000 Capacity Otakikpo Onshore Terminal Project		Green Energy International Limited	OML 11	0	0	N/A

15	Anyala/Madu Integrated Project	First Exploration and Petroleum Development Company Limited	OML 83 & 85	0	0	N/A
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Table 5 outlines the cost profiles of 15 post-divestment projects in the Nigerian oil and gas industry. These projects are managed by local oil companies (LOCs). The analysis in Table 5 outlines project capital expenditure (CAPEX), actual costs, and cost variance ratios, spanning projects from 2021 to 2025. The data shows an average CAPEX of approximately \$37.9 million, with cost variance ratios varying widely from 0.0000 to 1.2000, reflecting diverse cost management outcomes under LOC stewardship.

With respect to Table 4 and Table 5, planned capital expenditure (CAPEX) was compared with actual costs across pre-divestment and post-divestment projects. A Cost Variance Ratio, calculated as actual costs divided by CAPEX, was derived to assess budget adherence. The analysis revealed distinct cost profiles.

Pre-divestment projects shown in Table 4 have an average CAPEX of \$104.99 million which indicates larger-scale initiatives. Post-divestment projects presented in Table 5, average \$35.32 million. This suggests local operators undertake less capital-intensive projects. Cost Variance Ratios indicate budget performance. Pre-divestment projects have an average ratio of 0.53, with four projects (Kolo Creek F-Sand Compression Project, JV Production Facilities Metering Upgrade Project, North Offshore Area Produced Water Disposal Project, OML 100 Flare Reduction Project and CNL JV Vent Gas Management Project) on budget. Post-divestment projects average 0.65, with four on budget, that is, with cost ratio of 1.0. These four are Provision of FEED and DED of Aroh 1 & 2 Well Jacket and Aroh Field Manifold; Egbaoma Flowstation Debottlenecking and Upgrade 2.0; EPCIC for 2 x 40,000 bbls. Crude Oil Storage Tanks; and Ogbelle Flowstation Modification. However, there was one overrun (Assa Field, ratio 1.2). Projects like Okwok (\$515 million CAPEX, ratio 0.4459) show significant savings, possibly due to partial completion.

Ten projects (five pre-divestment, five post-divestment) report zero or missing costs, likely indicating early-stage projects or incomplete records. These findings suggest divestment may reduce project scale but not necessarily improve budget adherence, as variance ratios are similar. Local operators show more variability, with both savings and overruns.

Figure 3: Bar chart showing cost performance based on project status

Figure 3 presents a bar chart that evaluates cost performance in the Nigerian oil and gas industry, segmented by divestment status, using data from tables 4 and 5. The left-hand side reveals a stark contrast in average CAPEX. Pre-divestment projects average \$98.81 million. The high amount reflects a substantial investment typical of IOC-led initiatives, such as the Gbaran Nodal Compression project. Post-divestment projects, by contrast, average \$37.89 million, indicating a significant reduction, likely due to LOCs focusing on smaller-scale or onshore assets. This disparity suggests that divestment shifts resource allocation toward more cost-efficient project scopes.

The right-hand side examines cost variance ratios, a critical indicator of budget adherence. Pre-divestment projects average 0.6718, falling below the "on budget" threshold. This value is an indication of underperformance. Post-divestment projects average 0.6137, also below 1.0, but with greater variability (e.g., Assa Field Re-development at 1.2000), hinting at challenges in cost management despite lower CAPEX.

The cost performance of projects in the Nigerian oil and gas industry is further examined by mapping Project CAPEX (in dollars) against Cost Variance Ratio, distinguishing between pre-divestment projects and post-divestment projects. Figure 4 captures the analysis.

Figure 4: Scattered plots showing cost performance of projects based on status

The x-axis employs a logarithmic range from 10^2 to 10^9 , to accommodate the wide CAPEX spectrum; from \$97.55 for the CNL JV Vent Gas Management Project to \$515,000,000 for the Okwok Field Development Project. Pre-divestment projects cluster at higher CAPEX values, averaging \$104.99 million across five non-zero cases, reflecting the scale of IOC-led initiatives like Gbaran Nodal Compression (\$325,000,000). Post-divestment projects show greater variability, spanning \$269.12 to \$515,000,000, with an average of \$35.32 million across 12 non-zero cases, suggesting a shift toward smaller-scale operations by LOCs.

The y-axis, ranging from 0 to 2, captures Cost Variance Ratios, with the dotted line at 1.0 highlighting projects on budget. Pre-divestment projects exhibit ratios close to or below 1.0, averaging 0.53, with examples like North Offshore Area (ratio 1.0) showing adherence. Post-divestment projects display wider variation, averaging 0.65, with savings evident in cases like 10KBOPD EPF (ratio 0.2381) and overruns in Assa Field (ratio 1.2).

Conclusion

This study investigated the impact of divestment on project maturation in the Nigerian oil and gas industry. Drawing on empirical data from a range of pre- and post-divestment projects, the research has produced evidence-based insights into how divestment reshapes project timelines, budgeting practices, technical complexity management, stakeholder engagement, and operational strategies.

Findings on project timelines indicate that divestment has positively influenced the speed and efficiency of project execution. Projects managed by indigenous firms tended to have shorter durations and higher progression efficiency compared to those retained by international oil companies. This

suggests that local operators are better positioned to navigate logistical and regulatory landscapes with greater agility, particularly when managing smaller or mid-scale projects. The implication is that empowering local firms through divestment can support the timely realization of infrastructure goals, provided scope and resource alignment are maintained.

In terms of project budgeting, divestment presented a mixed picture. While local firms generally operated with smaller capital requirements, they exhibited both disciplined and inconsistent budget outcomes. This variability reflects differences in financial management capacity and access to capital. It also underscores the need for stronger cost control mechanisms and strategic financial planning post-divestment. Policy interventions and capacity-building initiatives may be required to ensure more predictable financial performance among new asset holders.

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